

Paving the way for more sustainable lithium-ion battery recycling routes

Marvin Gornik^a, Daniel Habermeier^a, Reiner Sojka^b, Nicolas Bucher^c, Denise Ott^{a,*}

^a EurA AG, Sustainability Division, Krämpferstraße 2, 99084, Erfurt, Germany

^b ACCUREC Recycling GmbH, Bataverstrasse 21, 47809, Krefeld, Germany

^c VARTA Varta Microbattery GmbH, Daimlerstr. 1, 73479, Ellwangen, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Lithium-ion battery recycling
LIB recycling processes
Industrial LIB recycling
Life cycle assessment (LCA)
Economic assessment
Circular economy

ABSTRACT

This study evaluates global, currently existing industrial lithium-ion battery (LIB) recycling processes from a technical, economic as well as environmental point of view. The focus lies in the comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) of these technologies in one single flexible model. Out of several analyzed publications, nine different industrial life cycle inventories were analyzed in detail and compared via LCA with similar system boundaries and background data. Minor adjustments were made to ensure a fair comparison. The results indicate variations in the degree of detail among the utilized inventories, with discrepancies observed, such as variations in coverage of pretreatment steps. This study identified trends indicating that hydrometallurgical treatments offer greater potential for reducing environmental burdens. This is primarily attributed to the wider range of materials recovered. Additionally, the LCA results of the complete life cycle of a LIB were analyzed using two different calculation approaches: the widely used End-of-Life (EoL) approach in LCA and the circular footprint formula (CFF), a recently introduced methodology by the European Union.

1. Introduction

By 2030, Europe is projected to face the challenge of recycling approximately 420,000 tonnes of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) annually, a significant increase from previous years (Thomas Schmalz). This surge is primarily driven by the widespread and growing adoption of electric vehicles and the expansion of renewable energy storage solutions. While managing this influx of waste poses logistical and environmental challenges, spent batteries also present an opportunity to recover valuable materials such as lithium, nickel, and cobalt, the latter being classified as a critical raw material by the EU. Therefore, the recycling of Li-ion batteries has attracted great attention. Beyond reducing resource dependency, battery recycling contributes to lowering the environmental footprint of LIBs (Sommerville et al., 2021), while also helping to secure the supply of key metals needed for future battery production (Dai et al., 2019a). However, to accurately assess the environmental impacts and benefits of LIB recycling, a harmonized Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) framework is essential.

Numerous LCA studies on the manufacturing and use phase of LIBs already exist (Ellingsen et al., 2014; Dai et al., 2019a; Le Varlet et al., 2020). Nevertheless, as of now, there remains a lack of consensus within the field of LCA regarding the analysis of environmental impacts

associated with batteries as well as the presentation of resulting data (Porzio and Scown, 2021; Peters, 2023). Studies use a variety of system boundaries, functional units, primary data sources (which in turn report data at different levels of granularity), LCIs and impact categories. This makes cross-comparisons between different technologies difficult and limits LCA's ability to create a feedback loop to early scientific research and technology development (Porzio and Scown, 2021). In 2023, Peters (2023) introduced a best practices framework for battery LCA, which offers a potential solution to harmonize various studies and facilitate comparisons among different literature sources.

A similar pattern is evident in the literature addressing battery recycling. Various recycling approaches are discussed in literature (e.g. Rinne et al., 2021; Quan et al., 2022; Dorri et al., 2022; Hao et al., 2017; Rajaeifar et al., 2021), yet system boundaries, analyzed impact categories, the exact cell chemistry of LIBs, scale of the process, data quality or functional units are not always comparable or even explicitly stated, as already described by Mohr et al. (2020a). Moreover, not all publications disclose the utilized LCI, hindering comparisons with other sources. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a comprehensive comparative LCA of different industrial-scale LIB recycling processes using data from nine industrial battery recycling processes. Additionally, it proposes key methodological refinements for future LCA

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: denise.ott@aura-ag.de (D. Ott).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2025.100344>

Received 16 April 2025; Received in revised form 25 September 2025; Accepted 2 October 2025

Available online 24 October 2025

2666-7894/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

studies on LIB recycling.

The paper is structured as follows: Following this introduction, Section 2 provides an overview of existing LIB recycling technologies, highlighting process variations and industrial developments. Section 3 outlines the LCA methodology and system boundaries, detailing how different recycling routes were assessed and presents the results and analysis of this study. Section 4 discusses key findings and offers recommendations for conducting LCAs in the field of battery recycling.

2. LIB recycling technologies

2.1. Introduction to LIB-recycling

Handling end-of-life (EoL) LIBs is a complex process that necessitates a multi-step treatment approach to ensure efficient material recovery. As demand for high-quality recycled materials increases, so does the need for specialized processing stages that refine and separate valuable components. In contrast, basic one-step methods, such as direct melting, result in low-purity, mixed outputs, limiting the potential for high-value reuse (Sojka et al.).

The LIB recycling process can be divided into three steps: preparation before recycling (separation of housing, sorting by subtype, disassembly of large stationary or automotive battery pack to module or cell level, discharging), pretreatment (mechanical and/or thermal treatment) and main processing (hydrometallurgy, pyrometallurgy or direct recycling). Fig. 1, which is adapted from Sojka et al. demonstrates different LIB recycling routes.

As shown in Fig. 1, several recycling routes exist. A comprehensive

review on unit operations involved, descriptions of industrially established recycling routes as well as advantages and drawbacks was conducted by Latini et al. (2022). In short, following the initial preparation and pretreatment phases, the main recycling processes start. Pyrometallurgy involves subjecting the entire battery to high temperatures (approximately 1500 °C) within a furnace to extract an alloy comprising valuable metals such as Ni, Co, and Cu. These metals can then undergo further refinement via hydrometallurgical processes to yield high-purity metal salts. The electrolyte undergoes evaporation within the lower temperature region of the furnace for energy reclamation, while plastics and graphite are incinerated at higher temperatures. Residual metals like Al, Mn, and a portion of Fe are contained within the slag fraction, typically utilized in lower-quality markets as additives in construction materials, although potential exists for refinement through hydrometallurgical processing. Hydrometallurgical recycling involves leaching typically via strong inorganic acids, such as H₂SO₄, supplemented with H₂O₂ as a reducing agent. This leaching process aims to dissolve cathode active materials into solution for recovery as battery-grade metal salts through techniques including crystallization, selective precipitation, solvent extraction, and electrochemical methods. In contrast to the pyrometallurgical approach, the hydrometallurgical route demands preliminary treatments such as dismantling, discharging, and electrolyte separation, followed by complex mechanical separations to reclaim various scraps of metals like Al, Fe, and Cu, with particular emphasis on extracting the black mass. The black mass serves as the starting point for direct recycling pathways. The approach of direct recycling involves the separation and subsequent regeneration of cathode (and anode) active materials without reducing them to elemental forms through leaching or

Fig. 1. Overview of schematized Li-ion battery recycling routes.

high-temperature treatments. The regeneration process aims to replenish the lost Li inventory in the cathode active material, maintaining particle morphology and crystalline structure to enable direct reuse in battery applications (Latini et al., 2022). Direct recycling offers great environmental and economic benefits but has not been established on a large industrial scale so far. One direct recycling approach which aims for industrialization is discussed in the following chapter.

2.2. Description of direct recycling technologies

The direct recycling of LIBs is an emerging technology aimed at preserving cathode and anode materials for reuse, rather than breaking them down into base metals as in hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical processes. The German company Erlos has taken a significant step toward industrializing direct recycling with the construction and opening of a small/medium scale industrial facility with a recycling capacity of 3500 t/a (Holding). Their approach focuses on a mechanical and chemical processing designed to recover cathode material for reuse in batteries with minimal degradation.

The Erlos process (Mohr et al., 2020b) begins with a complete disassembly of battery packs down to the cell level, a step primarily performed manually to ensure component integrity and safety. Following disassembly, pouch- or prismatic cells are processed in an inert gas-controlled environment, preventing thermal runaway or hazardous reactions during separation. Automated systems then open the cells, mechanically extracting anode and cathode layers. The cathode is treated with a sodium hydrogen carbonate solution under controlled pressure (max. 90 bar) and temperature conditions (20–30 °C), effectively detaching the coating from the aluminum foil. The resulting slurry is filtered and dried to yield recovered cathode material suitable for reuse in battery manufacturing. Similarly, anode material, primarily composed of graphite and copper foil, is processed through a cleaning and drying sequence. The recycled graphite currently has limited use in battery applications and can be rather used for other industrial purposes.

One of the key challenges in scaling direct recycling lies in material purity and consistency. Therefore, direct recycling might be more promising for the treatment of production scrap or at least pure material. Erlos addresses this by collaborating directly with OEMs (“WP Holding; “ERLOS), enabling consistent pure feedstocks of known composition. However, the need for reintroducing a portion of primary cathode material remains, as fully recycled active materials may exhibit slight variations in electrochemical performance. The mixing ratios are unknown, but according to the underlying patent (Schmidt et al., 2021), using 90 % recycled material, together with 10 % primary, achieves electrical characteristic values of 95 % compared to virgin material.

2.3. Comparison of industrial LIB recycling technologies from a technical and economic point of view

According to the EU-commission, recycling is defined as “any recovery operation by which waste materials are reprocessed into products, materials or substances whether for the original or other purposes” (Directive, 2008, 2018). Regarding LIB recycling, this refers to products after hydrometallurgical refining, i.e. a Ni/Co/Cu metal, sulphate, oxide, or carbonate depending on the process. Today, all industrial processes must pass through a hydrometallurgical treatment. Either solely in combination with a pretreatment step (mechanical or thermal) or in combination with an upstream pyrometallurgical main treatment. Therefore, the technical and economic comparison of processes is limited to pretreatment + hydrometallurgy or a combination of pyrometallurgy and hydrometallurgy.

If a thermal pretreatment step is not included in the recycling process or if batteries are not directly introduced into a high-temperature furnace, a preliminary discharging step typically becomes necessary. In principle, discharging prior to pyrometallurgical treatment or thermal pretreatment is not required, as both processes thermally neutralize the

cells and convert the stored electrical energy into heat. However, large EV or industrial batteries typically need to be dismantled beforehand, which is often done manually. In this context, skipping the discharging step poses safety risks for personnel. Therefore, discharging is generally required to ensure safe handling during dismantling. Given projections of approximately 420,000 EoL battery units requiring recycling in the EU by 2030 (Thomas Schmaltz), the practicality of scaling the discharging step may pose constraints on certain recycling routes, as accessing the battery management system (BMS) to diagnose and discharge high-voltage batteries is complex (Sojka et al.). Nonetheless, over-discharging steps to 0 V through electronic devices to recover the remaining electric energy of the battery are already performed on industrial level, e.g. by Duesenfeld (recycling capacity of 3000 t/a) (“Low energy consumption and highest), Redux (recycling capacity of 10,000 t/a) (“Lithium-Ionenbatterien,” REDUX), and Ascend Elements (recycling capacity of 30,000 t/a) (Wang et al., 2019; “Ascend Elements Innovation | Patented; AE). Otherwise, spent LIBs are effectively and easily discharged by soaking them in a conductive brine, resulting in the loss of the stored energy (Latini et al., 2022). Furthermore, zero discharge and dismantling approaches exist and made available commercially by the company BCA-industries under the name LithiBatt (“No Disassembly; “Full Turn). In this progressive approach, charged batteries or even battery packs are directly shredded under a water and nitrogen atmosphere.

It is crucial to make a clear differentiation between pyrolysis and pyrometallurgy. Pyrolysis involves thermal processes typically conducted within the temperature range of 200–800 °C, primarily resulting in the elimination of electrolyte organics, binders, and plastics through oxidation, yielding a gaseous phase. In contrast, pyrometallurgy entails extremely high-temperature smelting processes, surpassing 1000 °C, where also graphite is decomposed and all elements transition into a liquid state. This liquid state facilitates the separation of noble and less noble elements, with the former integrating into the alloy and the latter into the slag (Van Hoof et al., 2023). Thermal pretreatment or pyrolysis serves multiple purposes in the recycling of LIBs. One primary function is the removal of organic compounds, prior to hydrometallurgical processing. Additionally, thermal treatment facilitates the release of active material from the cathode foil by breaking down the strong adhesive polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF). Without this step, purely mechanical separation of PVDF adhered active material is often ineffective, leading to higher losses of the precious target metals. Furthermore, pyrolysis provides a controlled method for eliminating flammable and explosive gas mixtures that arise from electrolyte decomposition. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in neutralizing hydrofluoric acid (HF), which can be generated during battery breakdown. In contrast, if mechanical processing is used as the initial step, the handling equipment, including shredders, conveyors, and storage systems must be designed to withstand potential corrosion risks due to HF-gas formation in combination with moisture (Sojka et al.). Preventive measures, such as chemical neutralization with hydrated quicklime (Ca(OH)₂) or controlled suppression techniques are essential. Certain recycling processes, such as Duesenfeld’s inert gas shredding at temperatures below 80 °C (“DUESENFELD, 2022) have been implemented to minimize HF-gas formation (Low energy consumption and highest).

Pyrometallurgy integrates the benefits of thermal pretreatment and is less prone to fluctuations in the composition of the feedstock, to which hydrometallurgical processes are sensitive. It should be noted however, that to date, there is no industrially established process for recycling a mixture of various cathode-active materials (Tawonezvi et al., 2023). Pre-sorting to similar cell chemistry remains necessary. Nonetheless, invaluable elements like fluorine, phosphorus or silicon are technically challenging in hydrometallurgy, but are usually slagged in the pyrometallurgical step and, thus, removed. In the past, a major drawback of pyrometallurgy was the impossibility of recycling lithium, as it typically lands in slag. However, Umicore established a novel and patented pyrometallurgical process which allows the effective recycling of lithium

by recovery from flue dust with Na_2CO_3 (Van Hoof et al., 2023; Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022; Yagi and Scheunis, 2023). According to Umicore, the process proved its technical and economic feasibility and will be up and running in 2026 with a capacity of 150,000 t of spent LIBs at Europe's biggest battery recycling plant ("Umicore Battery Recycling").

Hydrometallurgical treatment possesses several challenges, notably due to its sensitivity to contaminants. Consequently, a common practice involves utilizing a combination of pyrometallurgical pretreatment followed by hydrometallurgy or at least a thermal pretreatment/pyrolysis followed by hydrometallurgy. In contrast to that, in 2022 Du et al. (2022) and Jiang et al. (2022) published industrially realized processes demonstrating hydrometallurgical treatment without a pyrolysis or upstream pyrometallurgy step. According to Du et al., the recycling processes of world leading battery recycling companies in China consist of manual disassembly of the battery pack, discharge, automatic disassembly of modules to cell level, crushing and vibration sieving to separate iron, aluminum, copper and separator from the black mass. Iron, copper, aluminum and the separator are further separated from each other by gravimetric, magnetic and eddy current separation. The electrolyte is evaporated by applying negative pressure, condensed, and subsequently incinerated together with the separator in a cracking furnace. The black mass is further separated into graphite, binders and the valuable cathode active mass. However, the cathode active mass is transported to a high-pressure reactor by a screw conveyor or belt conveyor for the hydrometallurgical treatment and reacted with sulfuric acid, water, and reducing agents (such as sodium sulphite). Then, after removing impurity ions such as iron and aluminum with the selective solvent extractant P204 (Di(2-ethylhexyl)phosphoric acid), manganese is extracted via a subsequent P204 line. Afterwards, cobalt and nickel are extracted with the solvent extractant P507 (2-Ethylhexylphosphonic acid mono-2-ethylhexyl ester), followed by ultrasonic degreasing and solution compound proportioning to finally obtain a purification consisting of nickel sulphate, cobalt sulphate, and manganese sulphate. Jiang et al. (2022) refers to another Chinese company with recycling capacities of over 100,000 t LIB per year and a slightly different process compared to Du et al. Their process involves manual disassembly of battery packs to cell level, crushing, drying with natural gas for electrolyte evaporation and decomposition, followed by air classification to separate aluminum, copper, separator and black mass. Afterwards, the black mass also runs through multiple leaching steps in the hydrometallurgical stage. As can be seen from these two examples, hydrometallurgy with a mechanical pretreatment step can be and already is implemented on a large industrial scale. Large-scale hydrometallurgical processes enable energy savings due to operation at lower temperatures. Furthermore, theoretically, all materials can be recovered, hydrometallurgical processes typically possess high recovery rates and even the recovery of electrolyte organics is possible.

As with any industrial process, the economic viability of battery recycling depends on the balance between costs—such as capital investment, labor, and operational expenses—and revenue, which primarily comes from the recovery of valuable materials, especially from the cathode active mass. The necessary investments and thus capital costs increase in the following order (Blömeke, 2022; Sojka et al.):

Pyrolysis + hydrometallurgy < pyrometallurgy + hydrometallurgy < mechanical pretreatment + hydrometallurgy.

Following this order, the process complexity increases. If the active mass recovered through shredding and classification is not treated via pyrolysis or pyrometallurgy, the hydrometallurgical process faces a higher chemical demand due to the presence of impurities that must be removed. To offset these challenges and maintain economic feasibility, scaling up recycling facilities with automated preparation steps, such as discharging and dismantling become necessary. Currently, the black mass derived from the pretreatment of EoL batteries is primarily processed in large industrial metallurgy plants with a processing capacity of 50,000 to 300,000 t/a (Sojka et al. Blömeke et al. (2022) investigated the economics and environmental burdens of mechanical pretreatment,

thermal pretreatment and pyrometallurgy, respectively followed by hydrometallurgy. They conclude that even though mechanical pretreatment possesses the highest capital costs, compared to thermal pretreatment or pyrometallurgy, mechanical pretreatment followed by hydrometallurgy has the highest economic benefit and avoids most environmental impacts. Bruno et al. (Bruno and Fiore, 2023) even conclude, that "hydrometallurgy presents the best economic and environmental trade-off compared to other recycling strategies."

3. Life cycle assessment of industrial LIB recycling technologies

To assess the environmental impacts and credits that are attributed to battery recycling, a comprehensive LCA according to the common standards ISO 14040:2006 (a) and ISO 14044:2006 (b) was performed. An LCA covers all the stages of the life cycle of a product, process, or service. The full life cycle of a product includes the extraction of resources, the processing of raw materials, transportation, the use phase, and recycling, up to the final disposal of remaining waste. Considering the study's specific emphasis on the EoL phase, the use-phase was intentionally omitted from consideration. It is important to note that this exclusion overlooks highly relevant factors such as efficiency and lifespan, which have a substantial influence on a battery cell's overall environmental performance. However, this deliberate omission serves to highlight the potential impact reduction achieved through recycling in the context of battery production.

The goal of this LCA was to compare actual industrially established battery recycling routes on a process level and finally their impact on the full life cycle of a battery. Furthermore, recycling pretreatment steps from literature were compared to thermal and mechanical pretreatment steps with data obtained from Accurec Recycling GmbH, a leading battery recycling company in Germany. Pretreatment refers to the breakdown from cell level to cell components and the valuable black mass. Only studies which disclose their inventory data on a mass basis (i. e. per kg battery cell) were chosen. Even though novel direct recycling approaches show a high potential in reducing the overall impacts of a battery, to date, no such approach was established on a large industrial scale with disclosure of life cycle inventory (LCI) data. Therefore, only hydro- and pyrometallurgical recycling routes were identified as suitable for this study. 18 papers were reviewed of which only nine LCIs were identified as suitable for comparison. A list of the reviewed papers and the reason for choosing or omitting them is given in Table S1 in the supplementary material. Literature research has shown that there is a lack in disclosure of data for pyrometallurgical processes. Older studies (Boyden et al., 2016; Dewulf, 2010; Hendrickson et al., 2015), but also more recent ones (Ciez and Whitacre, 2019; Cusenza et al., 2019) rely either on a non-comprehensive inventory of Fisher et al. (2006) or an outdated patent from Umicore (Cheret and Santen, 2007) which dates back to year 2007. This Umicore process has been replaced by a novel recycling route, which also enables the recovery of lithium. To circumvent these findings, an own process was modelled based on the recent Umicore pyrometallurgical recycling route with information from patents (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022; Yagi and Scheunis, 2023) and Van Hoof et al. (Van Hoof et al., 2023). It should be noted that this model does not reflect official data from the company and is solely based on secondary sources. Additionally, the LCI for a generic pyrometallurgical route, disclosed by the EU Joint Research Centre for calculation of the carbon footprint of batteries (Bassi et al., 2023), was considered. For a better comparability, the inventories found were implemented into a single LCA model, as described in the following section.

3.1. Modelling

The LCA was modelled and performed in the software Umberto 11 (LCA Software). Key modelling assumptions and methodological choices are summarized as follows: (i) a cradle-to-gate system boundary was applied for the recycling process comparisons, while a cradle-to-grave

approach (excluding the use phase) was used to evaluate full battery life cycles; (ii) the system boundary ends with the recovery of secondary raw materials (e.g., NiSO₄, CoSO₄, LiOH), excluding downstream refining or reuse; (iii) a consistent background system based on ecoinvent 3.9.1 (Wernet et al., 2016) with European datasets and average European electricity mix was used for all scenarios to ensure comparability across regional LCIs; (iv) the allocation of impacts follows the End-of-Life approach for individual process analysis and the PEF methodology for full life cycles, using EU-recommended A-factors (see Methodology for details). In the context of adhering to EU-compliant LCA practices, the PEF 3.1. method was chosen. According to the recommendations of the Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules for rechargeable batteries by the European Commission (Siret et al., 2018), the most relevant impact categories for the environmental analysis of batteries are climate change, resource use (energy carriers and minerals) and respiratory inorganics. Therefore, this study specifically targeted these categories in its analysis. Since the focus of this study lies in the EoL modelling, i.e., the recycling of the cell, a parameterized model for LIB recycling was developed. Within this single model, cell specifications (e.g., materials composition, energy density, etc.) and recycling options (e.g., recycling rate for each material in %) can be chosen. Once established, this approach enables a flexible model which can easily be arranged within a few clicks and scenarios can be calculated in a fast manner. The LCA model is schematically shown in Fig. 2 and briefly described below.

The LCA was modelled for production and recycling of an NMC811 pouch cell in Europe. 0.6 MJ Diesel was added to each LCI as a generic value for wheel loader operation (Dai et al., 2019b). Outputs from battery recycling were modelled based on the specified cells material content multiplied with recycling rates provided by the specific literature. If not provided by reference, recycling rates were taken from EverBatt (2023) (Dai et al., 2023). Additionally, waste outputs were modelled similarly for all recycling processes based on cell specification, materials used and recycled content. The only exception is the “Dust” output for the pyrometallurgical recycling based on Scheunis (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022), Yagi (Yagi and Scheunis, 2023) and Van Hoof (Van Hoof et al., 2023), since sufficient information on dust formation and composition was given in patent by Scheunis et al. (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022). In short, preliminary dust with a content of 90 % LiCl and 10 % CaCl₂ is reacted with Na₂CO₃ to yield Li₂CO₃ and NaCl. Li₂CO₃

is recovered while CaCl₂ + NaCl land in the dust. Stoichiometric calculations served as a basis for determination of the specific amounts, to which an excess of 10 % (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022) was subsequently applied for CaCl₂ and Na₂CO₃. Direct carbon dioxide emissions to air were also calculated stoichiometrically with carbon contents of the materials that are incinerated. While for pyrometallurgical recycling, graphite, binders, carbon black, plastics and electrolyte organics are fully oxidized to CO₂, for hydrometallurgy, only electrolyte organics are oxidized to CO₂, if not recycled as stated by Mohr et al. (2020a) For a fairer comparison, the system boundary ends with the same output materials recovered from recycling which are Al, Cu, NiSO₄, CoSO₄, MnSO₄, graphite, LiOH, electrolyte organics if their recycling rates are larger zero. Since some studies provided different outputs with their processes (e.g. Li₂CO₃ instead of LiOH), a materials conversion step was added which transforms the materials to the desired outputs. Additional material and energy consumption for this step were taken from EverBatt (2023) (Dai et al., 2023) model.

3.2. Life cycle inventory

Cell specifications were taken from the EverBatt 2023 (Dai et al., 2023) model for an NMC811 pouch cell. For modelling of the cell manufacturing, the ecoinvent dataset “battery cell production, Li-ion, NMC811 (RoW)” was adapted to align with the aforementioned cell specifications and an average European electricity mix was chosen to be in line with Europe as geographical scope. Data pertaining to the EoL phase/battery recycling was compiled from five industrial hydrometallurgical processes and four pyrometallurgical processes. Data gaps were filled with data or modelling approaches from the EverBatt 2023 (Dai et al., 2023) model. The full LCIs are listed in the supporting information S2. The inventories typically consist of mechanical pretreatment (crushing), several separation steps and the pyro- and hydrometallurgical treatment. While no formal sensitivity analysis was conducted, the study itself serves as a comparative sensitivity assessment by harmonizing background datasets and evaluating LCIs under consistent regional and methodological conditions. Variations in key impact drivers, such as electricity demand, recovery efficiencies, and leaching agents, were captured through the inclusion of nine literature-based process inventories, and error ranges are reflected in the result figures.

Fig. 2. Schematic view on battery recycling model, red circles = burdens, green circle = avoided burdens/credits, white circle = burden free input.

(see Fig. 5 and supporting information S2).

3.3. Methodology

In this study, two different methodologies for calculating the EoL phase were considered. The prevailing method widely employed to quantify the benefits of recycling within the context of a product's entire life cycle is referred to as the "End-of-Life (EoL) approach". In this approach, the benefits of recycling are calculated by multiplying the amount of recycled materials by the emission factor associated with the primary material initially utilized during the manufacturing phase. This calculated amount is then subtracted from the overall environmental impacts associated with the production of the product. For instance, if a product incorporates primary steel and 90 % of the steel is recycled during the EoL phase, the net environmental impact over the full life cycle of the product becomes nearly equivalent to that of a product employing only 10 % of the original primary steel. Nearly equivalent only, because burdens of the recycling process itself, transportation and waste management need to be considered as well. A major advantage of this straightforward approach is the easy calculation and concomitant, the results are easy to grasp for readers. Hence, for comparison of recycling pretreatment methods, as well as of complete recycling routes, the EoL approach is chosen. A major drawback however is, that manufacturers are credited for recycling solely by the recyclability of their product and not for their active efforts and commitment toward recycling or the utilization of recycled materials. In contrast, the EU-commission proposed the circular footprint formula (D.-G. for E. European Commission, 2021a) for assessing the EoL phase. Practitioners of LCA are required to employ this approach when applying the PEF method. In short, unlike the EoL approach where recycling credits are accounted for at 100 %, credits rely upon the A-factor. In PEF studies the A-factor values shall be in the range $0.2 \leq A \leq 0.8$ (D.-G. for E. European Commission, 2021b) and a few material-specific A values are published by the EU (Bassi, 2023; D.-G. for E. European Commission, 2021b). The A-factor aims to reflect market realities and depends upon the market's saturation with secondary material. The lower the A-factor, the higher the market's saturation with recycled material (i.e., the lower the demand for new recycled material). Thus, more credits are given to the use of secondary goods. Vice versa, the higher the A-factor, the less saturated the market and more credits are given to the recyclability of a product. A major advantage of the circular footprint formula is that it captures both aspects of recycling, the use of recycled content and a product's recyclability dependent upon market realities. Hence, it is more suitable for evaluations of full LCAs (i.e. from cradle to grave) and is therefore used in this study to estimate environmental performance of a battery when applying different recycling processes. However, a drawback is the more complex calculation and the difficulty non-LCA practitioners may have in understanding the results. The calculation and A-factors used in this study can be found in the [supporting material S2](#). The calculation follows the "Rules for the calculation of the Carbon Footprint of Electric Vehicle Batteries (CFB- EV)" proposed by Bassi et al. for the EU Joint Research Centre (Bassi et al., 2023).

The methodology employed for assessing EoL treatments must be selected and implemented carefully. A literature review by Nordelöf et al. (2019) has identified this as a weakness in several studies, which can result in double accounting of avoided burdens and subsequently introduce errors in conducted LCAs.

3.4. Results

3.4.1. Pretreatment

The pretreatment step takes place before the main processing (pyroand/or hydrometallurgy) and refers to the physical or thermal destruction of a cell to access the valuable active materials (Co, Ni, Mn). From the studies investigated, only Jiang et al. (2022) and Du et al. (2022) separately published data for pretreatment, while others only

published aggregated data for the complete process. The data obtained from literature was compared against an industrially established thermal/pyrolysis pretreatment and a non-industrially proven mechanical treatment from Accurec.

As shown in Fig. 3, the burdens of pretreatment mostly depend on the electricity consumption. Du et al. (2022) has remarkably higher impacts, as the electricity consumption is 4.5 times higher than that of thermal pretreatment. A reason for such high electricity consumption was not given by Du et al. According to the author however, the data was collected from two world leading battery recycling companies, located in Hubei and Jiangxi provinces in China (Du et al., 2022). During thermal pretreatment, carbon contents from binder, plastics and most of all from electrolyte organics are turned into pyrolysis gas and further oxidized to CO₂ in an afterburner. These emissions do not necessarily emerge in mechanical pretreatment on site. However, these materials are typically collected, disposed, and incinerated in further downstream treatments. Hence, the direct emissions from thermal pretreatment are compensated downstream in mechanical treatment. Therefore, also the mechanical treatment processes by Accurec and Jiang et al. (2022) almost solely benefit from a lower electricity consumption in comparison to thermal treatment and especially in comparison to Du et al. In general, to make a fair comparison between the different processes, the pretreatment should be considered in a more detailed, but especially comparable way. More complex pretreatment should therefore also result in higher quality materials/higher yields. However, the data available in the literature does not tend to allow these conclusions to be drawn, which affects the comparisons.

3.4.2. Full recycling processes

Following the integration of LCIs from studies by Mohr et al. (2020a), Jiang et al. (2022), Du et al. (2022), Dai et al. (2019 (Dai et al., 2019b) & 2023 (Dai et al., 2023)) encompassing hydrometallurgy and pyrometallurgy, alongside the inclusion of a modelled pyrometallurgical process based on Scheunis (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022), Yagi (Yagi and Scheunis, 2023) and Van Hoof (Van Hoof et al., 2023) into the LCA-Model, multiple analyses have been conducted.

As described in the methodology section in detail, the primary aim was to assess the recycling processes individually at the recycling process level. This approach was adopted to enable a direct comparison of the processes, without conflating the results with impacts from other life cycle phases such as production. To accomplish this, the impacts generated by the recycling processes were quantified through assessments of the utilized materials and energy (taken from the LCIs and additional estimates). Subsequently, the avoided burdens were determined with the "EoL approach" (see methodology) by considering the quantities of recovered materials and their corresponding emission factors associated with their primary production. The magnitude of the avoided burden can then be deducted from the impact value of recycling, yielding a total value, which serves as a basis for comparative analysis among the various recycling processes. This is depicted in Fig. 4. Large negative values (green bars) imply that the corresponding recycling process shows better environmental performance in the field of climate change.

The findings from Fig. 4 indicate that, on average (when Du et al. (2022) is included), the impacts from hydrometallurgical processes (mostly dominated by NaOH, H₂O₂, or other chemicals) slightly exceed those from pyrometallurgical processes, where directly emitted CO₂ emissions play a significant role. A robust comparison between different recycling approaches can be achieved by also considering the avoided burdens. Given the broader range of materials recovered (an overview of recovered materials per process is provided in the [supporting information S2](#)) by hydrometallurgical processes compared to pyrometallurgical processes, the avoided burdens associated with hydrometallurgical processes are higher. Consequently, this leads to a superior overall performance in terms of carbon emissions for hydrometallurgical processes. However, this trend does not hold for Du et al. (2022), as the

Fig. 3. Comparison of four different pretreatment methods for battery recycling in climate change total.

Fig. 4. Comparison of impacts/avoided burdens (climate change – total) of the recycling processes from literature.

impacts of recycling were excessively high. This notable disparity in the impacts, compared to other hydrometallurgical LCIs, stems from the considerable energy demand, especially for electricity from pretreatment and used steam in the precursor production. These two factors alone contribute to higher impacts than the combined inputs observed in the other hydrometallurgical processes.

Based on the total values depicted in the graph, it can be observed that among the hydrometallurgical processes, [Mohr et al. \(2020a\)](#), whose LCI relies on the German battery recycling company Duesenfeld GmbH, achieves the greatest reductions in CO₂ emissions. This is due to the recovery of the electrolyte solvents, as well as the relatively low impacts compared to other LCIs. As previously mentioned, Du et al. exhibits the least reduction potential, as the recovered materials can only partially offset the high impacts of the recycling process itself.

When comparing the pyrometallurgical processes, it becomes evident that the impacts of the modelled process based on publications by Umicore (Scheunis ([Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022](#)), Yagi ([Yagi and Scheunis, 2023](#)) and Van Hoof ([Van Hoof et al., 2023](#))) are slightly higher than the EverBatt processes. Despite exhibiting lower direct CO₂ emissions, additional impacts arise from natural gas and calcium chloride. However, owing to the capability of this process to additionally recover lithium, the total climate change saving potential is the highest among the evaluated pyrometallurgical processes. The pyrometallurgical treatment disclosed by the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) ([Bassi et al., 2023](#)), which according to JRC shall be used to calculate the carbon footprint of a battery, unless the “declarant is able to provide evidence that the batteries will be recycled in a specific recycling plant” ([Bassi et al., 2023](#)), shows the highest impacts and lowest credits among

Fig. 5. Averaged results (EoL- and PEF-approach) of impact category climate change for included hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical recycling processes.

the pyrometallurgical processes. Therefore, to circumvent the use of the JRC process and to improve the overall carbon footprint of a battery, battery manufacturers are urged to find more sustainable recycling methods for their products.

3.4.3. Full life cycle

To examine the impact of various recycling approaches on the entire life cycle (excluding the use phase) of an NMC811 LIB, the average outcomes for both hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical recycling processes were investigated. Their effects on the overall life cycle were assessed with two different recycling methodologies, the EoL approach and the product environmental footprint (PEF) method under usage of the circular footprint formula (see methodology for definition). The findings are illustrated in Fig. 5 for climate change. Results for other impact categories can be found in the supporting information S2.

Given the study's focus on recycling processes, the same dataset is utilized for the production of the NMC811 battery for the life cycles containing hydrometallurgy or pyrometallurgy. The error bars included indicate variations resulting from the averaging of the different assessed processes. For both methodologies used, it can be observed that, although the impacts stemming from the material/energy demand of the recycling processes (on average) are higher for hydrometallurgical treatment compared to pyrometallurgical treatment, the total result indicates lower values. This discrepancy is attributed, once again, to the broader range of recovered materials from hydrometallurgical treatment. To demonstrate the influence of the evaluation approach used, the results are presented based on the EoL approach (dark bars) and the PEF approach (light bars). As previously outlined in the methodology section, the impact of recycling is more evident in the EoL approach, as all resulting credits from recycling are accounted for, whereas the PEF approach only considers a specified portion of it, in accordance with the utilized A-factors. In contrast, the recycling impacts are always lower for the PEF approach, since also impacts are multiplied with the A-factors. In total, using the PEF approach, the carbon footprint of a battery over its full life cycle is less reduced through recycling than using the EoL approach.

Full life cycle impacts of an NMC811 battery (excluding the use phase) with various recycling approaches for four different impact

categories are depicted in Fig. 6. The results for each evaluated recycling process are displayed on the left side, while the averages for hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical processes are illustrated on the right. In these spider charts, life cycles incorporating pyrometallurgical recycling processes are depicted with a dashed line. At each corner of the charts, the life cycle with the highest impact in the respective impact category is displayed. Subsequently, the other processes are plotted proportionally, ensuring that the center point represents 0 %.

The left graph highlights again the already evaluated trend that the process based on Du et al. (2022) shows significant higher impacts than the other hydrometallurgical processes. Overall, the integration of hydrometallurgical recycling approaches yields better outcomes for *climate change* (−27 %) and *resource use, energy carriers* (−21 %). A clear trend emerges in the impact category of *respiratory effects*, wherein the inclusion of pyrometallurgical processes show significantly higher impacts. This arises from the capacity of hydrometallurgical processes to recover materials such as graphite and aluminum, which possess high impact-saving potential but cannot be recovered through pyrometallurgical recycling. This results in approximately 60 % less impacts on average in the category of *respiratory effects* for the hydrometallurgical approaches compared to the pyrometallurgical ones, thereby facilitating lower overall results.

Another notable observation from Fig. 6 is that both hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical recycling processes yield comparable outcomes in the impact category of *resource use, minerals and metals*. This similarity can be attributed to the recycling of copper, cobalt sulphate, and nickel sulphate. In the impact category of *resource use, minerals and metals*, these materials are the hot spots in battery cell production, and they can all be recovered in both recycling approaches, leading to comparable results. Additionally, since the impacts stemming from the recycling processes themselves exhibit low values in both treatments, the total results in this impact category are relatively similar.

4. Conclusion

In general, current recycling processes for EoL Li-ion batteries can be divided into three different process steps: preparation, pretreatment, main processing (pyrometallurgy, hydrometallurgy and direct

Fig. 6. Comparison of the life cycle with the different recycling processes in 4 impact categories from the reference package EF3.1.

recycling). To date, a variety of combinations of different pretreatment methods together with pyrometallurgy and/or hydrometallurgy exist on an industrial level, while direct recycling has not been established industrially on a large scale. However, promising technological developments have been achieved industrially over the last years within the pyro- or hydrometallurgical process route. For example, the implementation of mechanical pretreatment together with hydrometallurgy on a large scale, discharging of spent LIBs to 0 V through electronic devices with recovery of the remaining electric energy, as well as recovery of lithium from dust in a pyrometallurgical process. From a technical and economic point of view, pyrometallurgy has the advantage of a safe, scalable, and sophisticated process, which is suitable for different inputs, is less prone to contaminants and requires less capital investment costs compared to hydrometallurgy. Hydrometallurgy, however, offers the possibility of recovering more materials and despite higher investment costs, together with mechanical pretreatment, it is considered as the most economic recycling approach. To optimize existing LIB recycling processes and lead lab-scale technologies to market maturity, a circular economy needs to be created focusing on recycling all components (such as graphite or lithium). For Graphite, for virtually every quality level, there exists a meaningful second-life use outside of battery cell production, ranging from road construction to electrochemical sensors to advanced composite materials (Kosenko et al., 2023). When graphite recovery is technically feasible and material quality is transparently reported, incorporating second-life applications into LCA can reduce the environmental footprint of battery recycling. Moreover, processes should be automated to reduce health and safety risks while being able to treat different LIB dimensions and designs. Additional research needs to be conducted as in the field of direct recycling and collaboration between industry and academia is inevitable.

The LCA of multiple industrially established pyro- and hydrometallurgical recycling processes showed that despite major differences in energy consumption for several hydrometallurgical process routes, hydrometallurgy offers a better environmental approach on average. The reasons lie in the possibility of recovering more materials, compared to pyrometallurgy. Especially the process route from Mohr et al. (Duesenfeld GmbH) offers high reductions in environmental burdens, due to relatively low energy consumption and a clever pretreatment design, which even offers the ability to recover electrolyte organics for further processing in chemical industry. The goal of this study was to evaluate

and compare industrial LCIs for LIB recycling. Methodological limitations in this study must be acknowledged. Due to the limited availability of complete and disaggregated industrial LCI data, particularly for pyrometallurgical processes, some recycling routes were modelled based on secondary sources. Notably, one pyrometallurgical process was reconstructed using information from patents (Scheunis and Callebaut, 2022; Yagi and Scheunis, 2023) and scientific literature (Van Hoof et al., 2023). Additionally, the generic pyrometallurgical recycling process published by the EU Joint Research Centre (Bassi et al., 2023) was included as a policy baseline, although it does not represent a specific plant. While several hydrometallurgical LCIs were sourced from industrial processes, these datasets are often aggregated into single “black-box” models, lacking transparency between the three key process steps: preparation, pretreatment, and main processing. Moreover, information on output quality and recycling rates is often incomplete or missing. This limits the comparability of different recycling approaches and complicates in-depth life cycle assessments.

When conducting LCAs for LIB-recycling processes, it is beneficial to define input specifications (mass share of each material), recycling rates, output qualities (i.e., battery grade graphite or graphite for other purposes), disclose the LCI and to state the results on a mass basis (i.e., per kg spent LIB). When conducting LCAs for the full life cycle of a battery (i.e., from cell manufacturing over use-phase to recycling), number of cycles together with the depth of discharge and the energy density need to be specified and results should be stated on a mass basis and more importantly per energy (kWh) of the total energy provided over the service life by the battery. Furthermore, assumptions made, as well as calculation procedures should be disclosed transparently. These characteristics allow comparisons to other studies. Regarding LCA methodology, the EoL approach should be used when assessing the recycling process only, while PEF-methodology can be used for assessing the whole life cycle. However, it is important to know that due to the implementation of A-Factors the overall environmental impacts are higher for LCAs that use the PEF approach and can therefore not be directly compared to LCAs that use the EoL-approach. A direct comparison could lead to misleading interpretations regarding technical characteristics and environmental impacts of the recycling processes under investigation. Due to this incapability of comparison, as well as PEF-method still being in a development transition phase, LCAs with PEF-approach should also state results of the EoL approach.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marvin Gornik: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniel Habermeier:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Reiner Sojka:** Supervision. **Nicolas Bucher:** Supervision. **Denise Ott:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the financial support from the European Union (EU) under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe research and innovation programmes (grant agreement No. 875514 “ECO2LIB”, grant agreement No. 101193032 “BeyondBattRec”), financial support by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) due to an enactment of the German Bundestag (grant agreement No. 03XP0393A-J “IDcycLIB”) as well as joint Transnational Call 2023 of M-ERA.NET 3 (Horizon 2020 grant agreement No 958174 “LIB2SIB”).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2025.100344>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- T. AE, “Ascend elements | battery resourcers to open North America’s largest lithium-ion battery recycling facility by August,” Ascend Elements. Accessed: March. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ascendelements.com/battery-resourcers-to-open-north-americas-largest-lithium-ion-battery-recycling-facility-by-august/>.
- DIN EN ISO 14040, Environmental Management – Life Cycle Assessment – Principles and Framework (ISO 14040:2006 + Amd 1:2020); English Version EN ISO 14040:2006 + A1:2020, English Translation of DIN EN ISO 14040:2021-02. n.d.-a. Beuth Verlag GmbH. <https://doi.org/10.31030/3179656>.
- DIN EN ISO 14044:2021-02, Umweltmanagement - Ökobilanz - Anforderungen und Anleitungen (ISO 14044:2006 + Amd 1:2017 + Amd 2:2020); Deutsche Fassung EN ISO 14044:2006 + A1:2018 + A2:2020, Beuth Verlag GmbH. doi: 10.31030/3179656.
- Bassi, A., et al., 2023. Rules for the Calculation of the Carbon Footprint of Electric Vehicle Batteries (CFB- EV). Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Blömeke, S., et al., 2022. Material and energy flow analysis for environmental and economic impact assessment of industrial recycling routes for lithium-ion traction batteries. *J. Clean. Prod.* 377, 134344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134344>.
- Boydén, A., Soo, V.K., Doolan, M., 2016. The environmental impacts of recycling portable lithium-ion batteries. *Proced. CIRP* 48, 188–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2016.03.100>.
- Bruno, M., Fiore, S., 2023. Material flow analysis of lithium-ion battery recycling in Europe: environmental and economic implications. *Batteries* 9 (4), 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries9040231>.
- Cheret, D., Santen, S., 2007. *Battery Recycling*. US 7,169,206 B2.
- Ciez, R.E., Whitacre, J.F., 2019. Examining different recycling processes for lithium-ion batteries. *Nat. Sustain.* 2 (2), 148–156. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0222-5>.
- Cusenza, M.A., Bobba, S., Ardente, F., Cellura, M., Di Persio, F., 2019. Energy and environmental assessment of a traction lithium-ion battery pack for plug-in hybrid electric vehicles. *J. Clean. Prod.* 215, 634–649. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.01.056>.
- D.-G. for E. European Commission, 2021a. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the Use of the Environmental Footprint Methods to Measure and Communicate the Life Cycle Environmental Performance of Products and Organisations. European Union Luxembourg.
- D.-G. for E. European Commission, 2021b. Part C of Annex II of Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/2279 of 15 December 2021 on the Use of the Environmental Footprint Methods to Measure and Communicate the Life Cycle Environmental Performance of Products and Organisations. European Union Luxembourg.
- Dai, Q., Kelly, J.C., Gaines, L., Wang, M., 2019a. Life cycle analysis of lithium-ion batteries for automotive applications. *Batteries* 5 (2), 48. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries5020048>.
- Dai, Q., Spangenberg, J., Ahmed, S., Gaines, L., Kelly, J.C., Wang, M., 2019b. EverBatt: a Closed-Loop Battery Recycling Cost and Environmental Impacts Model Energy Systems Division. Argonne National Laboratory [Online]. Available: <https://www.anl.gov/amd/everbatt>.
- Dai, Q., Spangenberg, J., Ahmed, S., Gaines, L., Kelly, J.C., Wang, M., 2023. EverBatt: a Closed-Loop Battery Recycling Cost and Environmental Impacts Model Energy Systems Division. Argonne National Laboratory [Online]. Available: <https://www.anl.gov/amd/everbatt>.
- Dewulf, J., et al., 2010. Recycling rechargeable lithium ion batteries: critical analysis of natural resource savings. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 54 (4), 229–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2009.08.004>.
- Directive 2008/98/EC of the European parliament and of the council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain directives (Text with EEA relevance). <http://dat.a.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/98/2018-07-05/eng>, 2018–. (Accessed 15 March 2024).
- Dorri, I., Strømman, A.H., Nelson Manjong, L.U., 2022. Comparative LCA of Li-ion Battery Cells’ Recycling Processes,” Master’s Thesis in Circular Economy. Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Trondheim, Norway.
- Du, S., Gao, F., Nie, Z., Liu, Y., Sun, B., Gong, X., 2022. Life cycle assessment of recycled NiCoMn ternary cathode materials prepared by hydrometallurgical technology for power batteries in China. *J. Clean. Prod.* 340, 130798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130798>.
- Ellingsen, L.A., Majeau-Bettez, G., Singh, B., Srivastava, A.K., Valøen, L.O., Strømman, A.H., 2014. Life cycle assessment of a lithium-ion battery vehicle pack. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 18 (1), 113–124. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12072>.
- Fisher, K., Wallén, E., Laenen, P.P., Collins, M., 2006. *Battery Waste Management Life Cycle Assessment - Final Report for Publication*.
- Hao, H., Qiao, Q., Liu, Z., Zhao, F., 2017. Impact of recycling on energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions from electric vehicle production: the China 2025 case. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 122, 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.02.005>.
- Hendrickson, T.P., Kavvada, O., Shah, N., Sathre, R., Scown, C.D., 2015. Life-cycle implications and supply chain logistics of electric vehicle battery recycling in California. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 10 (1), 014011.
- Holding, W.P.. Pressemitteilung: sachsens Ministerpräsident Kretschmer zu Besuch bei ERLOS [Online]. Available: https://www.wphgroup.de/index.php?focus=STRATP_cm4all_com_widgets_News_29720799&path=?m=d&a=20240723102128-9646&cp=1#STRATP_cm4all_com_widgets_News_29720799. (Accessed 21 August 2024).
- Jiang, S., Hua, H., Zhang, L., Liu, X., Wu, H., Yuan, Z., 2022. Environmental impacts of hydrometallurgical recycling and reusing for manufacturing of lithium-ion traction batteries in China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 811, 152224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.152224>.
- Kosenko, A., Pushnitsa, K., Pavlovskii, A.A., Novikov, P., Popovich, A.A., 2023. The review of existing strategies of End-of-Life graphite anode processing using 3Rs approach: recovery, recycle, reuse. *Batteries* 9 (12), 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries9120579>.
- Latini, D., et al., 2022. A comprehensive review and classification of unit operations with assessment of outputs quality in lithium-ion battery recycling. *J. Power Sources* 546, 231979. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231979>.
- Le Varlet, T., Schmidt, O., Gambhir, A., Few, S., Staffell, I., 2020. Comparative life cycle assessment of lithium-ion battery chemistries for residential storage. *J. Energy Storage* 28, 101230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101230>.
- Mohr, M., Peters, J.F., Baumann, M., Weil, M., 2020a. Toward a cell-chemistry specific life cycle assessment of lithium-ion battery recycling processes. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 24 (6), 1310–1322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13021>.
- Mohr, M., Weil, M., Peters, J., Wang, Z., 2020b. Recycling of lithium-ion batteries. In: Bard, A.J., Stratmann, M., Gileadi, E., Urbakh, M., Calvo, E.J., Unwin, P.R., Frankel, G.S., Macdonald, D., Licht, S., Schiffer, H.J., Wilson, G.S., Rubinstein, I., Fujihira, M., Schmuki, P., Scholz, F., Pickett, C.J., Rusling, J.F. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Electrochemistry*, first ed. Wiley, pp. 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527610426.bard110009>.
- Nordelöf, A., Poulikidou, S., Chordia, M., Bitencourt De Oliveira, F., Tivander, J., Arvidsson, R., 2019. Methodological approaches to end-of-life modelling in life cycle assessments of lithium-ion batteries. *Batteries* 5 (3), 51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/batteries5030051>.
- Peters, J.F., 2023. Best practices for life cycle assessment of batteries. *Nat. Sustain.* 6 (6), 614–616. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01067-y>.
- Porzio, J., Scown, C.D., 2021. Life-cycle assessment considerations for batteries and battery materials. *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (33), 2100771. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202100771>.
- Quan, J., Zhao, S., Song, D., Wang, T., He, W., Li, G., 2022. Comparative life cycle assessment of LFP and NCM batteries including the secondary use and different recycling technologies. *Sci. Total Environ.* 819, 153105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153105>.
- Rajaeifar, M.A., Raugei, M., Steubing, B., Hartwell, A., Anderson, P.A., Heidrich, O., 2021. Life cycle assessment of lithium-ion battery recycling using pyrometallurgical technologies. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 25 (6), 1560–1571. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13157>.

- Rinne, M., Elomaa, H., Porvali, A., Lundström, M., 2021. Simulation-based life cycle assessment for hydrometallurgical recycling of mixed LIB and NiMH waste. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 170, 105586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105586>.
- Scheunis, L., Callebaut, W., 2022. Process for the recovery of lithium. US20220017990A1, Jan. 20. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20220017990A1/en>. (Accessed 13 February 2024).
- Schmidt, M., Goeckerlitz, M., Paesold-Runge, D., Goebel, F., Wienold, H., Mueller, P., 2021. Method for recycling lithium-ion batteries. US20210050634A1, Feb. 18. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210050634A1/en>. (Accessed 2 April 2024).
- Siret, C., Tytgat, J., Ebert, T., Mistry, M., 2018. Product environmental footprint category rules for high specific energy rechargeable batteries for mobile applications. *The Advanced Rechargeable and Lithium Batteries Association*.
- R. Sojka, Q. Pan, and L. Billmann, "Comparative Study of Li-ion Battery Recycling Processes".
- Sommerville, R., Zhu, P., Rajaeifar, M.A., Heidrich, O., Goodship, V., Kendrick, E., 2021. A qualitative assessment of lithium ion battery recycling processes. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 165, 105219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105219>.
- Tawonezvi, T., Nomnqa, M., Petrik, L., Bladergroen, B.J., 2023. Recovery and recycling of valuable metals from spent lithium-ion batteries: a comprehensive review and analysis. *Energies* 16 (3), 3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031365>.
- Dr Thomas Schmaltz, "Recycling of lithium-ion batteries will increase strongly in Europe," Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI. Accessed: February. 17, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.isi.fraunhofer.de/en/blog/themen/batterie-update/recycling-lithium-ionen-batterien-europa-starke-zunahme-2030-2040.html>.
- Van Hoof, G., Robertz, B., Verrecht, B., 2023. Towards sustainable battery recycling: a carbon footprint comparison between pyrometallurgical and hydrometallurgical battery recycling flowsheets. *Metals* 13 (12), 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13121915>.
- Wang, Y., Gratz, E., Sa, Q., Zheng, Z., Heelan, J., 2019. Method and apparatus for recycling lithium-ion batteries. US10522884B2, Dec. 31. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10522884B2/en>. (Accessed 27 March 2024).
- Wernet, Bauer, Steubing, Reinhard, Moreno, Ruiz, Weidema, 2016. The ecoinvent database version 3 (part I): overview and methodology. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.* <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>.
- Yagi, R., Scheunis, L., 2023. Recovery of nickel and cobalt from Li-ion batteries or their waste. US20230250511A1, Aug. 10. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US20230250511A1/en>. (Accessed 13 February 2024).
- Ascend elements innovation patented hydro-to-cathode process increases material performance and value," Ascend Elements. Accessed: March. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ascendelements.com/innovation/>.
- Duesenfeld - Eco-friendly recycling lithium-ion batteries. Sep. 15. <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/duesenfeld-ecofriendly-recycling-of-lithiumion-batteries/252981241->. (Accessed 28 March 2024).
- ERLOS – EA green energy." Accessed: February. 18, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ea-green-energy.com/erlos/>.
- Full turn-key solutions for industrial shredding & recycling." Accessed: July. 17, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bca-industries.com>.
- LCA Software - Ökobilanzen für Experten | Umberto," iPoint. Accessed: June. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.ipoint-systems.com/de/software/umberto/?gad_campaignid=13648912717&hscam=13648912717&cHash=b9e109cf31b9823f0ad8d5278e398b37.
- "Lithium-Ionenbatterien," REDUX - smart battery recycling. Accessed: March. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.redux-recycling.com/de/services/lithium-ionenbatterien/>.
- Low energy consumption and highest recovery rates." Accessed: March. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.duesenfeld.com/recycling_en.html.
- No disassembly (or discharge) required: shredding the largest EV battery packs in one system – the industrial news report. https://industrialnewsreport.com/2025/01/no-disassembly-or-discharge-required-shredding-the-largest-ev-battery-packs-in-one-system/?utm_source=chatgpt.com. (Accessed 17 July 2025).
- Umicore battery recycling." Accessed: March. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.umicore.com/en/newsroom/news/umicore-battery-recycling/>.
- WP holding, WPH-Gruppe, WP spedition, WP logistik, Erlos, WP Fahrschule - AKKURECYCLING." Accessed: April. 2, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://510737186.swh.strato-hosting.eu/AKKURECYCLING/>.